

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article the comparative typology of phraseological units in Uzbek and English are analyzed. Due to the fact that phraseological units are enriched along with the vocabulary of the language, each language has its own phraseological units and they are reflected in the daily life and lifestyle of each nation. Phraseological units in Uzbek and English are compared with examples.

Key words: phraseological units, stable word combinations, phraseological meaning, lexis, semantical feature, affixes

Introduction

Language has become a main means of communication since the humanity appeared in the world, and in the process of speech, people use words, phrases, fixed phrases, and phraseological units. As phraseological units are enriched together with the vocabulary of the language, each language has its own phraseological units, and they are reflected in the daily life and lifestyle of each nation. Phraseological units are compounds that differ from other units of the language and have their own meaning and form. Unlike words and free combinations, they are syntactically integral and semantically invariant. Phraseology can be cited as a treasure of a certain language. After all, phraseology is figurative language units that show the history, culture and uniqueness of a nation. Phraseological units mainly reflect the customs and traditions of the nation.

Comparative analysis of phraseological units in Uzbek and English

There is no language without phraseological units. Phraseology has recently emerged as an independent discipline in linguistics. Its formation is inextricably linked with the names of famous linguists. It is worth saying that the theories developed by V.V. Vinogradov, N.N. Amosova, A.V. Kunin, N.M. Shansky, T.N. Fedulonkova play an important role in elucidating current problems in the field of phraseology. In Uzbek linguistics, a number of scientific research has been carried out on the linguistic nature of phraseology, lexical-grammatical features, as well as the translation of phraseology in literary works, the problems of interlanguage translation. In this regard, Sh.Rakhmatullayev, B.Yuldoshev, A.Mamatov, S.Mirzakulov, Sh.Abdullayev, N.Ormonova, D.Hoshimova conducted a number of studies. Uzbek linguist Sh. Rakhmatullayev "A phrase is a large linguistic unit, consisting of at least two independent words (lexemes). Accordingly, the expression plan of the phrase is defined as the words (lexemes) and the linguistic units contained in them [2, 24]. So, a phraseological unit is a word combination or a combination equivalent to a sentence consisting of two or more words, semantically related to each other and used figuratively.

Examples of phraseological units in English were first used in literature. When translating some works of fiction from one language to another, it became impossible to translate inseparable word combinations. Then phraseological units in those languages were

studied. The term phraseology was first used in philology in 1558 by the English writer Neander. Neander was forced to use this term when translating literary works. Although the majority of phraseological materials are included in dictionaries and other sources, research works on the theory of phraseology are rarely found in linguistic sources.

When analyzing the linguistic and cultural characteristics of phraseological units in English and Uzbek languages, the national-cultural characteristics of phraseological units are defined as additional linguistic factors. Both in English and in Uzbek, many phraseological units are expressed in the people's lifestyle, customs, and national characteristics. For example, the English phrase "**to throw up one's cap**" when translated into Uzbek means "**throw one's cap(do`ppi) to the sky**" [1, 65]. In fact, "cap(do`ppi)" is not a hat, but this word is used to express the national identity of the two languages. As mentioned above, the words or units of the phraseological units are selected based on the vocabulary and lifestyle of each nation.

Comparative analysis of "numbers" used in Uzbek and English phraseological units

Numbers also play a key and important role in phraseological units. In particular, if we compare the use of numbers in English and Uzbek phraseological units, we can see that numbers depend on the religion and lifestyle of each nation. For example, the idiom "be on cloud nine" in Uzbek means "to fly on the ninth sky" or "to feel on the ninth sky", i.e. "very happy, satisfied" [1, 125]. This idiom shows that the number "**nine**" is a miracle number in English. The Uzbek version of this phrase is "to fly in the seventh sky", and Sh. Rakhmatullayev's "Explanatory Phraseological Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" interprets it as "happy, very satisfied". It can be seen that for the Uzbek people, not the number **nine**, but the number "**seven**" means miracles and magic.

In English a wide range of numerals such as two, four, five, six, eight, fifty, hundred are commonly used in phraseological units to form a "human" concept. The numbers one and two are the most productive numbers in the English phraseological units. The use of these numbers is mostly determined by logic and reality. The semantic modification of English numerals in terms of phraseological combinations is manifested in their ability to change each other, to implement different quantitative filling (Two Heads are better than one; four eyes see more than two), to be used in the stylistic devices of antithesis, hyperbole (thousand pardons; one to thousand) [3, 153].

Conclusion

Any language cannot be imagined without phraseological units and idioms. Phraseological units are related to the culture, history, lifestyle of each nation, and they develop and increase together with the nation. Such stable units make a person's speech fluent, and serve to enrich a person's imagination in fiction. Phraseological units reflect the entire history and way of life of this people, so writers often refer to them. Phraseological units are an alternative methodical tool to make the language of an artistic work juicy and impressive. In addition, they serve to make the speech fluent and impressive, idiomatic, figurative. Therefore, every English language learner should learn phraseological units, and this will make their speech more fluent and give them the opportunity to think and think in this language.

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